

LIBRARY ORIENTATION AND USER ENGAGEMENT: A CASE STUDY FROM GASHU'A, YOBE STATE

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Abstract: Academic libraries, as integral components of higher educational institutions, are entrusted with the pivotal role of acquiring, processing, organizing, disseminating, and safeguarding a vast array of information sources, encompassing both print and non-print materials. This comprehensive mission is geared towards satisfying the diverse informational needs of the academic community, including faculty, students, and researchers. In response to the ever-evolving landscape of library collections and the rapid progress in information handling, retrieval, and utilization technologies, academic libraries have formulated strategic initiatives and programs to cater to the information requirements of their users. The ultimate aim is to enrich the teaching, learning, and research endeavors of the academic populace. However, in light of the constant expansion of library holdings and the adoption of cutting-edge information technologies, there arises a compelling necessity to provide comprehensive library orientation to newly-registered library users. The user base of academic libraries encompasses students, staff, and researchers, many of whom may lack the essential skills and knowledge required to effectively harness the resources at their disposal. Absent proper library orientation, users may encounter difficulties in identifying, locating, accessing, or navigating the library's extensive collection.

It is noteworthy that academic libraries extend their services beyond the mere provision of information resources. They also create a conducive environment that supports reading, reference, and consultation, facilitating the exploration of existing work in related subject areas and staying abreast of ongoing research in their areas of interest. The library's role in this regard is twofold – employing both traditional methodologies and the integration of modern technology to enhance accessibility. This confluence of approaches allows users to access information via networks using computers and other contemporary tools, ensuring a seamless and efficient research experience.

This paper delves into the critical importance of library orientation in academic libraries. It highlights the indispensable role of these institutions in fostering effective teaching, learning, and research, emphasizing the role of library orientation in bridging the gap between users and the wealth of resources available in these libraries.

Keywords: Academic libraries, library orientation, information literacy, academic community, information resources.

Introduction

The library is one of the functional organs of higher institutions charged with the responsibility of collecting, processing, organizing, disseminating and securing all sources of information (print and non-print) to meet the needs of all members of the academic community (staff, students and researchers). The academic libraries as it is called developed strategies and programs towards meeting the informational needs of its community to enhance teaching, learning and research activities of the academic community. Considering the continuous growth in library collections and technological advancement in information handling, retrieval and use, there is the need to give adequate library orientation to newly registered library users. The users of academic libraries are made up of students, staff, and researchers who may not have any skill or knowledge on how to utilize the library materials. Without library orientation, it may be difficult for the users to identify, locate, access, or find

their way in the library. The library provides not only the information resources but also conducive environment for the use of the resources for their reading, reference, and consultation in the attempt to find what others have done in similar subject area and what is going on in researches and on the same subject of interest to readers. This is done by library in the provision of services either with the traditional strategies and or in combination with the application of modern technology to enable readers to have ease of access via network using computers and other tools.

Madukoma (2013) commended that library orientation was introduced in academic institutions to ensure that students have the intellectual ability and skill to access and retrieve information as well as construct a framework for learning and research purposes. The impact of library orientation goes beyond the number of years that students spent in academic institutions.

It transformed all learning and research activities of students, staff, and faculties or departments. It has a lifelong impact on library users and enables them to acquire library skill to be able to locate, access, evaluate, retrieve and use library materials with ease. It is a process of educating the users to use information that is available in the library to their advantage. Although, the method of application of library orientation differs from library to library, but the main purpose is to enable users to become independent and skillful in identifying, accessing and utilizing library resources effectively. In most academic libraries for example, Federal University Gashu'a and College of Education Gashu'a, Yobe State, Nigeria, Library orientation takes place at every new semester beginning in October each year according to Nigeria institutional calendar. The target group for orientation at such time is the newly recruited students into FUGA and COEGA respectively. All recruited 100 level and NCE 1 students into various courses of the both institutions would be taken through the various divisions, units and sections of the libraries to see themselves the physical resources entail to aid their learning, assignment, research activities and how to utilize those information resources.

Statement of the Problem

Most of FUGA and COEGA newly admitted students come from public school with different backgrounds some of which possess little better skills to utilize library materials, while others have no skill for utilizing library materials such as retrieving appropriate books from shelves, computer, use of internet and library catalogue. The both institutional library conducts library orientation programs in every first semester of each session but still there are some students who face difficulties in accessing and use library materials. They take long time to ask and go around the shelves for searching of particular resources. This situation made researcher to embark on this study, with the hope of finding why these students are not responding positively to the orientation given to them. Do they really understand the orientation exercise? Is the orientation program relevant to the needs of library users? What are the challenges facing library orientation in academic libraries? These are some of the questions this research is going to tackle. The answer to the research will hopefully be used to improve the skills of the users, so that the materials in the library can be put into maximum utilization.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the effects of library orientation on the library users
2. Identify students' perception on library orientation program

Research Question

To achieve the purpose of this research, the study was guided with the following research questions:

1. What are the methods used for library orientation in academic libraries?
2. What is the effect of library orientation on the library users?
3. What are the challenges facing library orientation in academic libraries?

Review of Related Literature

Many authors have stressed the value of academic library orientation program at their libraries. Despite clear evidence that students produce higher quality academic research. Hindagolla (2012) discloses that although the library provides a number of services and facilities for its users, the majority of students are not aware about most library services owing to the limited coverage of the orientation program. In addition, the students are not satisfied with the existing library orientation programs due to different factors such as un-suitable time slots, in-sufficient awareness on e-resources, in-sufficient coverage of study areas, too much students for one group, insufficient information of the program and limited

duration of the program. Similarly, Bamidele (2015) Opined that librarian can develop reading and library use plan by involving into a series of lectures under library orientation and user instruction program. Esse (2014) and Ullah (2014) submits that the program aid the library users to become independent learners in utilizing library resources. Wickramanayake (2014) stated that most academic libraries had no better financial support to aid library orientation programs. He further stated that they lack facilities such as projector, computers and good working environment in their academic libraries for the implementation of library orientation. He also noted, though most academic librarians needed to implement library orientation programs for their institutions, they suffered from lack of funds to support the program, lack of physical and human resources and training.

Madukoma(2013) reported that library orientation was introduced in academic institutions to ensure that students have the intellectual ability and skill to access and retrieve information as well as construct a frame work for learning. The impact of library orientation goes beyond the number of years that students spent in institutions. It has a life –long impact on library users and enables them to acquire library skill to be able to identify access, retrieve and use library materials with ease. Bhatti (2010) commended that effective library orientation links naturally to active learning techniques and life-long learning. Active learning as a method of educating students that allows them to participate in class, takes them beyond the role of passive listener and note taker and to take some direction and initiative with the aid of library orientation. Orientation in the use of library plays the most crucial role to enhance quantitative and qualitative use of libraries to library users. The term orientation as used in this research work includes not only how to locate information but also instruction on the use of library tools, explanation of library policies and introduction to library resources and services to newly admitted students into higher institutions. Bleidt (2011) Opined that library orientation by institutional libraries used to improve student performance, retention and graduation rate with the aid of library orientation. Oakleaf (2011) added that academic libraries also support students' achievement to augment and support their grade point average (GPA) and professional/educational test score.

Library Orientation in Academic Institutions

Library Orientation is a vital program which is usually carried out by academic librarians. Goldman (2016) narrated that newly admitted students who receive an orientation to library resources and services are more likely to seek needed research assistance with course papers, assignments, projects, and presentations. The main objectives of library orientation are to expose students to the library services and its resources and to educate and guide them on how to utilize the library services and resources. The orientation usually takes place within the both library buildings, where students were grouped department by department in order to have control over their population. The program provide opportunity to newly recruited students about activities, services, programs, resources, opening hours, contact information, rules and regulations of the libraries. During each orientation programs, newly admitted students were given the privilege to ask questions on any issue concerning the library activities that had not been clearly understood by them and answers were adequately provided by the librarians.

Effect of Library Orientation on Library Users

The implementation of library orientation in higher education in the past and presently has impacted positively to newly admitted students in Nigeria Institution including Federal University Gashu'a (FUGA) and College of Education Gashu'a (COEGA) on how to utilize the available resources of the library at the appropriate time. Busayo(2013) observes that students of Nigeria higher education particularly the academic libraries are being inducted to explore the library and information service in different ways so that they can be comfortable, free minded and potential in accessing library resources. Suleiman (2012) and Madukoma (2013) stated that academic libraries in Nigeria and other developing nations in the world had developed some methods for orientation on its new and current users. The

methods include library orientation, classroom teaching, instruction, guided library tour and library guide. How these methods have positively impacted the users' considering trends and proliferation in information provision and adoption of modern technologies in academic libraries is a matter of concern. The present method of library orientation in both institutions indicated that, the library users were set to be self-independent in searching for information resources in the library. It was also observed that, majority of the students who received training through library orientation program were familiar with reference section of the libraries which seems to be difficult to some library users before each commencement of the library orientation. The effect of library orientation on library users are as follows:

1. They become self-independent in search of information resources in the libraries
2. Increase academic performance
3. Borrowed and returned library materials on or before the due date
4. Aids user not to violate rules and regulations of the library
5. Improve productivity of users within and outside the institutions
6. Expose users to various section and unit of the libraries
7. Allow users to appreciate and value libraries in their learning activities.

Omeluzor (2017) posited that the aims and objectives of library orientation on library users is to expose them to the library services and its resources and to educate and guide them to effectively utilize the library services and resources.

Challenges Facing Library Orientation in Academic Libraries

Library Orientation is an indiscriminate situation. This is due to the fact that academic libraries and librarians are currently facing unprecedented challenges and problems. Apparently, the reason for these changes is the development and introduction of new information literacy initiatives in the field, the rapid development of information and communication technology sector and the complex nature of user requirements. With the current trends in library services and with the importance of library orientation on library users, several challenges have being identified in research as factors downgrading against it in academic libraries.

Anyaoku (2015) identified student's apathy to library orientation as a problem in academic libraries. Idoko (2015) elaborated that several challenges as noted by staff and students including lack of confidence in the use of library, librarian's mode of instruction not adequate to help students and inadequate information resources for learning e.g computers among others. The lack of modern technological tools such as projector, computers, internet and many more to facilitate the programme of library orientation in Federal University Gashu'a (FUGA) library has given limited support in carrying out the programs effectively and efficiently. Okoye (2013) suggested that library orientation in higher institutions across Nigeria revealed that the major challenges facing the program include lack of practical and demonstration on the use of the internet to conduct research, inadequate ICT facilities in teaching and inadequate number of professional staff to conduct library orientation.

Research Methodology

The researchers gathered data from Federal University Gashu'a (FUGA) and College of Education Gashu'a (COEGA). The data was gathered through the instrument of a questionnaire. Sixty (60) copies of the questionnaire were randomly distributed for equal representative of students across the institutions. Data were analyzed using frequency and percentages. The entire 60 (100%) questionnaire were returned and considered usable.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The entire 60 (100%) questionnaire admitted to the respondents were returned and considered useable. Out of the 60 respondents 42 (70%) of the respondents were males and 18 (30%) respondents were females. It can be seen from table 1 that males respondents were more in number than the females.

Table 1: Distribution of users by gender

Sex of users	Frequency	Percentage
Male	42	70%
Female	18	30%
Total	60	100%

Table 1 reveals that there were more males than the females' respondents which confirm the view that FUGA and COEGA are dominated by the male students.

Table 2: Methods used for library orientation in your institution

Methods used for Library Orientation	Used		Not used		I don't know	
	F	P	F	P	F	P
Classroom teaching	60	100%	0	0%	0	0%
Library orientation	44	73%	13	22%	3	5%
Guided library tour	0	0%	42	70%	18	30%
One-on-one teaching	20	33%	26	43%	14	24%
Social media	18	30%	31	51%	11	19%
Library website	0	0%	46	77%	14	23%
Total	142	236%	158	263%	60	101%

Result in table 2 shows that, the method that were mostly used for library orientation in both institutions were classroom teaching 60(100%) library orientation 44(73%) one-on-one teaching 20(33%) and social media 18(30%) were the methods mostly used. The result also revealed that guided library tour 0(0%) and library website 0(0%) were not used for library orientation, while some of the respondents indicated that they did not know about them.

Finding is closely related to the study of Omeluzor, Akibu, Dika and Ugangwa (2017) in their study of methods, effect and challenges of library instruction in academic libraries discovered that most of academic libraries use classroom teaching for their library orientation. This result raise concern about the future of ICT use in library orientation since most of the modern methods was not used. The implication of this result is that library users will not have the advantages of learning and understanding how to utilize all the library services at their disposal. None-use of the modern methods will also affect library user's ability to identify easier way of accessing the library and its resources. FUGA and COEGA should endeavor to educate its users with modern methods to increase the learning, teaching and research of the library users.

Table 3: Effect of library orientation on newly library users

Effect of library orientation	SA		A		D		SD	
	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P
It has greatly improved my ability to identify, access and retrieve information that is available in the library	38	63%	18	30%	3	5%	1	2%
Library orientation enhances my reading skills and turn me in to a regular library user	32	53%	21	35%	5	8%	2	4%
It also exposed me to different bibliographic databases available in the library	15	25%	25	42%	2	3%	18	30%
Library orientation made me become aware of the scope of the library resources	36	60%	21	35%	3	5%	0	0%

It has at the same time improved my academic performances	43	72%	17	28%	0	0%	0	0%
It also made me become aware of the values of libraries in my academic pursuit and long-life-learning	32	53%	19	32%	7	12%	2	3%
Total	196	326%	121	202%	20	33%	23	39%

Key: SA =Strongly Agree, A =Agree, D =Disagree, SD =Strongly Disagree

Table 3 indicated that library orientation has positive effect on the library users and improved their use of library information resources. The results shows that respondents indicating that they strongly agreed marked the highest rate with 196(326%) followed by agreed 121(202%), strongly disagreed 23(39%) and disagreed 20(33%). This study is closely related to the study of Esse (2014) in his study effect of library instruction on satisfaction with the use of library and its services discovered that library orientation program have a significant effect to library user in their understanding of the library and its uses.

Table 4: Students perception on library orientation program

Options	SA		A		D		SD	
	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P
Relevant	37	62%	21	35%	2	3%	0	0%
Very relevant	22	37%	19	32%	17	28%	2	3%
Irrelevant	5	8%	3	5%	33	55%	19	32%
Very irrelevant	0	0%	0	0%	22	37%	38	63%

Key: SA =Strongly Agree, A =Agree, D =Disagree, SD =Strongly Disagree

Data from table 4 reveals that 37(62%) of the respondents strongly agreed that library orientation is very relevant to them, followed by 2(3%) disagreed that the program is relevant to them, 22(37%) strongly agreed that library orientation is very relevant, followed by agreed 19(32%), disagreed 17(28%), strongly disagreed scored 2 (3%) and irrelevant scored 5(8%). Finding is closely related to the study of Suleiman (2012) in his study discovered that library orientation is of very relevant to library users in discovery the appropriate information resources on the shelves and internet.

Table 5: Challenges of library orientation program in FUGA and COEGA libraries

Statement	SA		A		D		SD	
	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P
Inadequate classroom/space for the program	2	3%	6	10%	18	30%	34	57%
Over population	16	27%	12	20%	21	35%	11	18%
Lack of instructional materials for the program	53	88%	7	12%	0	0%	0	0%
Un-conducive environment for the program	23	38%	21	35%	9	15%	7	12%
Limited time allocated for the program	12	20%	11	18%	16	27%	21	35%
Student negative attitude towards the program	32	53%	18	30%	8	14%	2	3%
Inadequate and qualified staff for the program	5	8%	7	12%	27	45%	21	35%

Lack of enough fund to support the program	46	77%	11	18%	3	5%	0	0%
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Key: SA =Strongly Agree, A =Agree, D =Disagree, SD =Strongly Disagree

The users responses did not discriminate widely across the numerous challenges of library orientation. In spite of this, inadequate classroom for the program 2(3%) strongly agree with the challenges, while 53(88%) strongly agree lack of instructional materials for the program as the most numerous challenges. More than half of all the respondent recommended from the questionnaire issued to them that, inadequate technological facilities, poor network/internet connectivity, outdated library collection and poor power supply from both institution constitute challenges to their use of the library. All other challenges were similarly agreed or strongly agreed upon by one-third to half of the respondents.

Summary of findings

From the findings, it is obvious that the institutions put in place several methods to educate library users which range from library orientation, classroom teaching, one-on-one teaching and social media. This is in line with what Esse (2014) posited that library orientation is a program which equips library users with the skills to enable them to be independent and sophisticated users of libraries and their resources especially in the areas of identification, location, search, retrieval and exploitation of information. The result however showed that library orientation has greatly improved their academic performance and enhanced their reading skills and turned them into regular library users. The users are of the perception on library orientation program that it is of relevant to their academic activities such as assignment, project and also enlighten them on the values of libraries in their academic pursuit and long life learning.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study established that library orientation enable the library to sensitize the newly admitted students and create adequate awareness about the available resources and services of the library to meet and satisfy the needs of the users. Likewise, library orientation that is well organized will create confidence in the users and therefore encourage them to use the library effectively. The aim of library orientation encompasses making the library users skillful in research as well as life long learner. The effect of library orientation goes beyond the classroom and orientation but rather making the users to engage themselves and have the ability to identify, access, retrieve and use library information resources effectively to their advantage. Library orientation is an effective means of educating the users and creating awareness of available information resources in the library. Therefore, viable methods and media such as library website, social media, text messaging, emailing should be explored to meet with the current trend.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Considering the importance of library orientation to the use of library, it is recommended that library orientation should be given more priority in the institutional library in order to sensitize more students and draw their attention to the available resources and services that can be of immense benefit to them in the course of their studies

2. Academic libraries should redesign library orientation program to impact students' academic activities

3. Students should always create time to attend library orientation program organized by the academic libraries, either as orientation, seminar or special training sessions on new services. This will afford them the opportunity to acquaint themselves with the general library environment which will further encourage effective library use

4. Academic libraries should endeavor to use ICT in the delivery of library orientation to the library users to faster communication and access to the librarians and library information resources

The management of both institution should support the program with funds and facilities that would better improve and put to use to satisfy the user needs as well as utilized for the education and sensitization of patrons

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